

Machine learning predictions of Target Off-Block Time and Aircraft Turnaround Duration for all European CDM Airports

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Abstract—The target off-block time (TOBT) is set by airlines or ground handling agents and indicates the aircraft departure time at collaborative decision making airports (A-CDM). This time should be updated when deviating by at least +/- 5 minutes (the typical tolerance window) from a previously released value. Possible TOBT updates can be due to rotational reactionary delays, delays during ground operations, technical and unexpected issues, and/or late arrivals of passengers and crew. These factors make TOBT predictions challenging, although highly desired for pre-tactical and tactical planning. For a main case study, this paper presents a machine learning (ML) model predicting TOBT and turnaround durations across all European CDM airports. Results show that overall 66% of TOBT predictions did not require any update by an operational user with an average absolute error, recorded at the end of the turnaround processes, of 4.3 minutes computed over 2023 operational data. A first validation exercise and ongoing shadow mode live trials are confirming the expected model performance. An additional case study explores the potential to enhance TOBT predictions by incorporating, as additional input data of the model, ground delay information and passenger data supplied by Austrian Airlines.

Keywords—Turnaround; Target Off-Block Time; Machine learning; trials

I. INTRODUCTION

Airport Collaborative Decision Making (A-CDM) is a set of procedures involving real-time data sharing among airport operators, air traffic controllers (ATCs), ground handlers, airlines and the network manager (NM). It is currently fully implemented in 33 airports across Europe and aims to improve efficiency, reduce delays, and enhance overall airport operations through coordinated decision-making and resource management [1].

In A-CDM, a target time links to a milestone, marking an agreement among partners to meet specific deadlines, thus aiding decision-making for downstream events [2]. A key milestone, the target off-block time (TOBT), indicates when an aircraft will be ready for departure (doors should be closed, boarding bridge removed and pushback vehicles available and ready to start-up). To optimize runway throughput and ground movements, ATC assigns each flight a Target Start-

up Approval Time (TSAT) that either matches or exceeds the TOBT, in accordance with relevant regulations [1].

The release of TOBTs is optional between 3 and 2 hours before estimated off-block time (EOBT) [3] (via Early departure planning information messages, known as Early-DPIs) while it becomes highly desirable at later stages (via Target-DPIs) [1]. If a TOBT value is 15 minutes or more later than the last EOBT, a DLA / CHG message should be sent. Airlines can delegate to the NM the filing of DLA messages based on this logic [4]. In most CDM airports, a delegated ground handling agent is responsible for updating the TOBT whenever the time deviates, typically by more than +/- 5 minutes from the previously released value.

TOBT values could be postponed because of rotational reactionary delays, aircraft technical issues, crew delays, passenger delays, issues during ground operations such as deboarding, boarding, cleaning, catering, fueling, issues with pushback equipment availability, and other unexpected events [5]. A Eurocontrol CODA report [6] indicated that the average departure delay per flight in 2019 was 13.1 minutes, with 3.4 minutes attributed specifically to delays caused during turnaround operations (IATA delay codes 11-19, 21-29, 31-39). TOBT may be updated if a significant number of passengers is arriving on a delayed connecting flight. Specifically, airlines may choose to delay a departure to accommodate these passengers, thereby avoiding the need for re-booking and ensuring both passengers and their luggage reach the final destination. Boarding and deboarding operations are critical and affected by passenger behaviors. During these operations, ground delays can be triggered, leading to TOBT updates.

The manual entry of TOBT is susceptible to errors due to human limitations sometimes leading to last-minute adjustments. As ground operations become increasingly complex, turnaround coordinators face greater challenges in keeping TOBT updates aligned with frequent micro-adjustments for each aircraft. This often leads to last-minute TOBT changes, which tend to alter the TSAT calculation resulting in late calculated takeoff times (CTOT) with minimal opportunity for improvement. The combination of these elements creates significant challenges in predicting TOBT values for both

operational users and modellers.

This paper presents the key results of the OpTT2.0 (Optimisation of Turnaround Time) project, which was initiated in response to a proposal from Swiss International Air Lines within one of the EATIN (Eurocontrol Air Transport Innovation Network) initiatives (<https://www.eurocontrol.int/project/eatin>). The project builds on the successful handover of the OpTT1.0 model [7] to Prague Airport, where it is currently used to automate the release of TOBT via DPI messages. OpTT2.0 was kicked off in September 2023 and is supported by 13 European airports and 7 airlines.

For the main case study, a ML model predicting the last TOBT release and turnaround duration for all the European CDM airports is presented. The second case analysed the potential gain in model performance when predicting the turnaround duration including passengers data (provided by Austrian Airlines) and delay information. The paper is organized according to the following structure: in Section II, a literature review on turnaround time predictions is presented; Section III includes information about the algorithms used for the model's development. In Sections IV and V a description of the two case studies and of the models is provided. Finally, Section VI includes the discussion of the results and the conclusions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The turnaround time represents the difference between the off-block time of a departing flight and the in-block time of the same aircraft on the previous inbound flight and includes all ground handling activities such as passenger deboarding and boarding, luggage unloading and loading, refueling, cleaning, catering, water supply, power supply, and maintenance checks. Often, aircraft turnaround is defined as the difference between the actual off-block time (AOBT) and the actual in-block time (AIBT). However, several definitions can be found in the literature, considering other timestamps indicating the beginning and end of turnaround duration [8]. As an example, for the beginning of the operations modellers could consider the scheduled in-block time (SIBT) or the sum of the taxi-in and estimations of arrival times [9], while for their conclusion, the scheduled off-block time (SOBT) or the TOBT [7], [3].

Several works in the literature focus on modeling turnaround sub-processes [10], [11], [12], [13]. These studies typically employ stochastic probability functions based on historical data, discrete event simulation, and synthetic data generated through agent-based simulation methods [8].

Predicting turnaround durations at a given moment requires the ability to accurately link inbound and outbound flights, which is one of the main challenges in modeling this process. Identifying aircraft rotations is not always straightforward, as neither scheduled flight times nor flight plan information alone provide a clear indication. Once this challenge is addressed, the modeler can use the scheduled in-block and off-block times to generate an initial turnaround estimate.

However, these scheduled turnaround values may not always reflect actual operational conditions. One method for scheduling turnaround duration involves adding buffer time to the estimated minimum turnaround time [14]. This buffer serves to accommodate potential delays caused by inbound flights or occurring during ground operations, although it can be imposed by scheduling constraints. An analytical approach was developed in the POEM project [15]. Here, the minimum turnaround time was calculated as the 2nd percentile from actual turnaround distributions of historical data, categorized by airport size, wake turbulence category and aircraft operator. For the same problem and with a similar approach, also the 5th percentile of actual turnaround times distributions has been used [16].

In another project, predictive models were created to estimate the minimum and nominal turnaround time durations. A combination of regression and classification techniques was employed, and the models' outputs were merged using convolution to generate a probability distribution [9].

Turnaround time durations can also be inferred from the predictions of two separate models: one forecasting the aircraft arrival time and the other predicting the departure time. In [17] and [18], for example, two machine learning models predicting inbound and outbound flight delay distributions during the pre-tactical phase using historical operational data were developed. Although it was not explicitly presented in the work, as soon as inbound and outbound flights can be linked by the same aircraft registration, the predictions of the such models could be used to predict the turnaround duration defined as the difference between the AOBT and the AIBT.

The duration of turnarounds is influenced by several unpredictable factors, including passenger behavior, availability of airport resources, and unexpected maintenance activities [5]. These factors contribute to the uncertainty in both assessing actual turnaround times and forecasting them reliably. Authors in [19] explore strategies to enhance aircraft turnaround efficiency by focusing on reliable and optimized passenger boarding processes, highlighting the importance of minimizing boarding delays through better planning, advanced technologies, and streamlined operations, ultimately reducing overall turnaround time and improving airline performance. In [20], the authors model the turnaround processes and calculate the likelihood that a turnaround is completed within a given Target Off-Block Time (TOBT) using mathematical convolution, incorporating uncertainties of individual processes. Similarly, in [21] and [14], the authors use Monte Carlo simulations to identify critical paths in the turnaround process and consider operational uncertainties. In another work [7], the uncertainty of single ML predictions was estimated using a combination of regression and classification models. Here, it was shown that the average uncertainty computed over the testing data samples was proportional to the root mean squared error (RMSE) of their predictions. The study also focused on the comparison of the performance of individual airport-specific models with that of a single model designed for all the airports of interest showing promising

results. This aspect of model generalisation will be further analysed in this paper (Section IV).

III. ALGORITHM FOR MODEL DEVELOPMENT

In ML, boosting algorithms improve model accuracy by combining multiple weak learners to create a more robust model. They generate training sets assigning higher probability to samples misclassified by previous models, helping to reduce bias [22]. CatBoost [23] was selected as the algorithm for the studies presented in this paper (Sections IV, and V). CatBoost is a gradient boosting algorithm that stands out for its native support of categorical features and strong generalization capabilities. Unlike many traditional boosting methods, CatBoost does not require extensive pre-processing such as one-hot encoding. Instead, it employs an efficient strategy based on target statistics, combined with a technique known as ordered boosting. In conventional gradient boosting, each model in the sequence is trained on the same dataset, which can lead to overfitting caused by using the same data to both compute target statistics and train the model. Ordered boosting addresses this by training on different permutations of the dataset. For each data point, the model only uses information from previous examples in the permutation to compute its target statistics. Another key strength of CatBoost lies in its computational efficiency and scalability, with optimized implementations for both CPU and GPU environments. It also handles missing values and text features, making it particularly versatile for real-world datasets that include a mix of variable types.

The performance of this algorithm was evaluated against LightGBM and XGBoost [24], with results indicating that CatBoost model was slightly better than the others (with approximately 2% improvement of the main metrics). Models are evaluated using loss functions, which quantify the difference between predicted and actual values (errors). In regression problems, MAE is often chosen because it treats all the errors equally without emphasizing larger ones. In contrast, root mean squared error (RMSE) loss function applies a quadratic scoring rule, which places greater emphasis on outliers. For the presented model, the mean absolute error (MAE) loss was used [25]. CatBoost hyper-parameters, such as maximum depth and the number of trees, are optimized as they significantly influence the loss function. K-fold cross validation (CV), was employed to assess model performance according to a specific set of hyper-parameters. It involves partitioning the dataset into k folds, training the model on k-1 folds, and testing on the remaining fold. GridSearchCV [26] was used to find the best hyper-parameters by evaluating all possible combinations among predefined values. At the end of Section IV-A, the selected hyperparameters are described.

IV. TOBT AND TURNAROUND TIME PREDICTIONS FOR ALL EUROPEAN CDM AIRPORTS

This study builds on a prior research [7] in which a set of models predicting turnaround duration and the last release of TOBT were developed using operational data provided

by Prague, Fiumicino, Arlanda and Geneva airports showing that the same level of prediction quality could be achieved with a unique generalised model trained on data from all four airports. Inspired by this research, this case study describes the development of a single ML model predicting turnaround duration and the last release of TOBT, suitable for all European A-CDM airports and for the airlines operating from them.

A. Regression ML model

The model presented in this case study was trained using the entire set of 2023 Eurocontrol flight progress messages containing information from the integrated initial flight plan processing system (IFPS) and from the Enhanced Tactical Flow Management System (ETFMS) [3]. From these data a list of input features has been extracted, as described in Table I. Here the acronym $EOBT_{first}$ refers to the estimated off-block time extracted from the first filed flight plan [3]. For the initial model development the SOBT was used as an input. However, due to the impossibility of gathering this information from Eurocontrol systems during trials, this input was substituted by the first $EOBT$ value filed in a flight plan (this substitution did not compromising model performance). The estimated in-block time ($EIBT$) is calculated as the sum of statistical taxi-in values and the arrival time available from the flight progress messages. Only once the aircraft reaches the parking stand this input is substituted by the $AIBT$. The input feature *type of arrival time* allows to distinguish between the different types of arrival time information of the inbound flight: calculated, estimated and actual, which appear in the flight progress messages when the flight model is, respectively, calculated, estimated or actual. The *aircraft operator* and the *operating aircraft operator* differ when flights are operated by a delegated operator on behalf of a main one. Weather information such as, wind speed, temperature, visibility distance, dewpoint, rain, snow, and fog intensity was included as input data in the first phase of model development and later removed since their contribution to the predictions was negligible (assessed by SHAP analysis and metrics).

The target of the model is the difference between the last released $TOBT$ value and the $EIBT$ (or $AIBT$ once the aircraft is in-block). Additionally, since the in-block time is estimated primarily based on the information provided in flight plan updates, the model also enables the prediction of TOBT itself by adding the model's output to the estimated in-block time upon release of the prediction.

The set of inputs listed in Table I does not allow to capture events that might trigger TOBT updates during the turnaround itself, as these events are unpredictable and not suitable for inclusion in a predictive model. However, airlines often postpone the $EOBT$ in flight messages when delays or issues occur during the turnaround. In such cases, it is preferable to use the $EOBT$ release as a TOBT forecast rather than relying on the model's prediction. Therefore, a rule was incorporated into the model's logic to output the current $EOBT$ release

TABLE I. INPUT FEATURES USED FOR MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Input feature	Description
Available Turnaround time	$EOBT_{first}$ - EIBT or AIBT
Aircraft Type	Categorical
Hour of operations (at EOBT)	Categorical
Month of operations (at EOBT)	Categorical
Day of the week (at EOBT)	Categorical
Operating aircraft operator	Categorical
Aircraft operator	Categorical
Airport identifier	Categorical
Great Circle Distance (gcdOrig)	From origin airport (Km)
Great Circle Distance (gcdDes)	To destination airport (Km)
Type of arrival time	Categorical
Model output	Description
Turnaround duration	$TOBT_{last}$ - EIBT or AIBT

when it indicates a later time than the TOBT predicted by the model.

The tuning process for this model using five folds (Section III) led to two hundred estimators and fifteen edges (maximum depth) as optimal hyper-parameters.

B. Metrics & Results

In A-CDM, a recommended tolerance window is of ± 5 minutes, meaning that a TOBT update is not required if the actual occurrence of the event falls within this timeframe.

Therefore, three metrics are considered for the assessment of model performance: the percentage of predictions with an error less than or equal to 5 minutes (in absolute value); the MAE (Equation 1) which is a standard metric for regression problems, where y_i represents a target value and \hat{y}_i a predicted one [25]; the standard deviation of the error (Equation 2), where e_i represents the model error of the single observations and μ the average of the errors computed over the testing dataset. The latter metric is a measure of how tightly or widely the errors cluster around their mean error. Small standard deviation values indicate that the model's predictions are more consistent and vice versa. The results presented in this section apply to both turnaround duration and TOBT predictions since they are generated by the same model and obtained by adding the predicted turnaround duration to the in-block time, as explained in Section IV-A.

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{n} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_i - \mu)^2} \quad (2)$$

Model predictions are available as soon as a flight plan is filed, and it is possible to link the inbound and the outbound legs with an aircraft registration. The predictions update over time as the arrival time of the inbound flight calculated in ETFMS changes, causing the available turnaround time to vary. Results at the network level, measured as averages across the 33 CDM airports, indicate that overall 66% of predictions at the end of the turnaround operations fall within the tolerance window without requiring any further update by

an operational user. Overall, the MAE of the error calculated at the same time horizon is 4.3 minutes.

It is important to note that the model's performance measured at the end of turnaround operations is largely comparable to that observed at the beginning. This is expected, as the model does not receive any additional input data during the turnaround process that could be used to refine its predictions in real time. However, due to the logic implemented in the system - where the Estimated Off-Block Time (EOBT) overrides the predicted Target Off-Block Time (TOBT) if the EOBT is later - a modest improvement in performance was observed. Specifically, there is a 3–4% reduction in Mean Absolute Error (MAE) when comparing the performance at the end of turnarounds to that at the beginning. Nevertheless, this refinement does not translate into a meaningful improvement in the proportion of predictions with an absolute error of five minutes or less, which remains unchanged.

Figure 1 shows the model performance for all the A-CDM airports and for the top 20 airlines (i.e., those with the highest number of turnaround operations) operating from them. The maximum and minimum values of predictions falling in the 5 minute tolerance window were recorded respectively for Brussels and Charles de Gaulle airports (with a percentage of approximately 83% and 56% as shown in Figure 1a) and for Iberia and British Airlines (with a percentage of approximately 82% and 61% as shown in Figure 1c). In terms of MAE, the maximum and minimum values were recorded for Charles de Gaulle and Palma de Mallorca airports (respectively 6.2 and 2.9 minutes in Figure 1b) and for Air France and Iberia airlines (respectively 5.4 and 2.6 minutes in Figure 1d).

Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) are used in machine learning to explain and interpret the contributions of individual features to a model's predictions, providing insights into how each feature influences the output [27]. Figure 2 is a SHAP summary plot. Each point on this plot represents a SHAP value for a feature and an instance in the dataset, showing its effect on the prediction compared to the base value. Features are listed on the y-axis and ordered by their importance. The x-axis shows the SHAP value, which represents the impact on the model's prediction: values to the right increase the prediction, while values to the left decrease it. The color represents the feature value, with blue indicating lower values and red higher values. Categorical and boolean features are in grey since no magnitude can be associated with them. As a result, the *available turnaround time* is the most influential feature, meaning that the availability of turnaround time significantly affects the model's predictions. The large spread of SHAP values suggests it can either strongly increase or decrease the prediction. Other features such as *hour of operations*, *Great Circle Distance* calculated from the airport of interest to the destination airport, and *aircraft operator* also play an important role.

at the two time horizons. A deeper analysis showed that the reason for high standard deviation values on the disrupted day at earlier time horizons (e.g., around four hours before takeoff time) was related to a small percentage of flights impacted by high AFTM delay that was first imposed and then removed, causing wide shifts of model predictions. Overall, the lower values of the standard deviation for model predictions suggest a lower presence of outliers and a higher consistency over time compared to user's releases until 50-40 minutes before takeoff time. Finally, the last metric indicates that 61% and 68% of predictions, respectively, on the disrupted and nominal day featured an error (in absolute value) lower than or equal to 5 minutes at the end of turnaround operations.

It is important to observe that in our analyses, we typically observe an increase in model error when considering earlier time horizons. This is because the model produces predictions based on the estimated arrival time of the inbound flight at a specific point in time. As flight plans evolve, the estimated arrival time may change due to delays or other reasons, leading to adjustments in the predicted turnaround duration and the TOBT of the outbound flight. However, the recorded error, as measured by our evaluation metrics, remains the difference between the final TOBT release and the model's prediction using the arrival time information available at the original prediction time.

Please note that for this exercise we did not extract information from Early and Predicted-DPI messages, which are released earlier than 2 hours before EOBT. The few observations recorded between four and two hours before EOBT correspond to Target-DPIs of flights that experienced significant delays before takeoff.

D. Second validation exercise

Following the successful replay validation exercise, the model has been integrated into Eurocontrol's validation environment, NMVP (<https://www.eurocontrol.int/simulator/nmvp>), where it now operates using live operational data. Since January 13th, project stakeholders have had access to a platform that allows to test the model in shadow mode [28] (Figure 5). This platform provides information on inbound and outbound flights, aircraft rotations throughout the operational day, model predictions and their updates over time, as well as the operational messages exchanged between stakeholders and Eurocontrol.

Results for the ongoing trials are shown in Figure 6 where the metrics are computed as average values across the 33 CDM airports in Europe. In Figure 6a, it is possible to observe that the model error progressively decreases from 6.4 minutes (measured four hours before takeoff) to 4.3 minutes recorded 10 minutes before takeoff time (approximately at the end of turnaround operations if one considers an average of 10 minutes taxi-out). Overall the MAE generally decreases as takeoff time approaches, meaning both the model and users provide more accurate predictions closer to departure. The highest errors occur at earliest time horizons, where

Figure 3: Average model performance (MAE) computed at the network level as a result of the replay validation exercise. The model was tested using operational data from (a) a nominal day (the 10th of October 2023) and (b) a non-nominal day (the 13th of October 2023). Values above the bars indicate the percentage number of TOBT values, with respect to the total of the day, that either the model (first value) predicts or that the users (second value) provide (extracted either as TOBT itself or as the difference between the TTOT and the taxi-out).

uncertainty about the arrival time of the inbound flight is higher. The model and user errors follow similar general trends. The model error is comparable to the user error across most of the intervals, suggesting that the model performs at least as well as user estimates. However, in the final minutes before takeoff (during the turnaround phase), user error becomes lower than model error. This behavior is expected since users progressively refine their estimates as they approach the final release, whereas the model lacks the capability to capture last-minute operational factors, such as ground delays, that may require TOBT adjustments.

On the contrary, the standard deviation of the model error seems to be overall lower than the one of the user's release (precisely until 50 minutes to takeoff), indicating a higher consistency over time of model predictions (Figure 6c). Figure 6b shows that the percentage of predictions within the tolerance window gradually increases as the takeoff time approaches, rising from 58% at 240 minutes before takeoff to 67% at 10 minutes before takeoff. A similar pattern can be observed for the user releases. However, the user error is consistently higher than the model error, indicating that user adjustments lead to slightly better adherence to the tolerance window.

For this second validation exercise, information from Early and Predicted-DPI messages was also extracted, unlike in

Figure 4: Standard deviation of the error values computed as an outcome of the replay validation exercise. The model was tested using operational data from (a) a nominal day (the 10th of October 2023) and (b) a non-nominal day (the 13th of October 2023). Values above the bars indicate the percentage number of TOBT values, with respect to the total of the day, that either the model (first value) predicts or that the users (second value) provide (extracted either as TOBT itself or as the difference between the TTOT and the taxi-out).

the first validation exercise. Specifically, the users' values were either extracted from Target DPIs as TOBT releases or computed from Early and/or Predicted DPIs as a difference between the target takeoff time (TTOT) and the taxi-out. This explains the higher number of turnaround occurrences identified as being released by users at earlier time horizons (e.g., starting from 4 hours before takeoff). These values can be observed above the bars in Figures 3 and 6.

V. TOBT PREDICTIONS USING PASSENGER AND DELAY DATA

Airlines can decide to postpone the TOBT while waiting for late passengers. Sometimes problems during the de-boarding and boarding operations due to the number or to the type of passengers might cause TOBT updates. It is also known that ground delays occurring during turnarounds can trigger TOBT updates. This study focuses on the influence of passenger and delay data on the capability to predict the TOBT.

A. Data and Model Development

Three ML models were developed to analyse the influence of passengers and delay information on the predictability of the TOBT using passenger data for flights operated by Austrian Airlines at Vienna airport. The Eurocontrol CODA team, instead, provided data about the types of delay for the

departing flights of interest. The first model was developed using data from 2022, with the input features described in Table I (except for information about the aircraft operator and airport and with the addition of the *scheduled turnaround* defined as SOBT - SIBT). For the second model, passenger data (listed in Table II) were added to the set of input features while in the third model, the types of ground delay (IATA delay codes 11-39) were introduced as inputs (Table I) under the assumption that the model could be provided at inference time with information about the delays as soon as they occur. Passengers with a connecting time of 30 minutes or less, along with their luggage, were considered critical due to the higher likelihood that their delays could necessitate postponing the TOBT. In Table II, type f indicates passengers connecting onto flights operated by other airlines, type c those connecting onto flights operated by Austrian airlines and other airlines in business class, while type y those connecting onto flights operated by Austrian airlines and other airlines in economy/premium economy class.

The CatBoost regression model was set up with 200 trees and a maximum depth of 6.

TABLE II. INPUT FEATURES DESCRIBING PASSENGER AND GROUND DELAY INFORMATION. UP TO 5 TYPES OF GROUND DELAYS FOR A SINGLE FLIGHT WERE INCLUDED IN THE MODEL AS AN INPUT

Passenger Data	Description
De-boarding pax (#)	Numerical
Boarding pax (#)	Numerical
Wheelchair de-boarding pax (#)	Numerical
Wheelchair boarding pax (#)	Numerical
Identifier of departing gate	Categorical
Critical connecting pax type f (#)	Numerical
Critical connecting pax type c (#)	Numerical
Critical connecting pax type y (#)	Numerical
Critical luggage (#)	Numerical
Delay Data	Description
Ground delays IATA code	Categorical

B. Results

Table III presents the results of the three models developed using Austrian Airlines' data. When comparing the results, the basic model, evaluated at the AIBT, has the highest MAE of 4.3 minutes and the least percentage of predictions falling within the tolerance window of ± 5 minutes (71%). Adding passenger data reduces the MAE by 7% while the inclusion of delay information reduces the MAE by further 5%. Overall, the latter model improves the performance of the basic model by 10% in terms of MAE and by 7% in terms of % predictions that have an error contained in the window ± 5 minutes.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF DIFFERENT MODELS EVALUATED BASED ON THEIR MAE AND THE PERCENTAGE OF PREDICTIONS FALLING WITHIN THE TOLERANCE WINDOW OF ± 5 MINUTES

Model type	MAE (min)	% predictions in tolerance window
Basic	4.3	71
Basic + Pax data	4.0	74
Basic + Pax + Delay data	3.8	76

Orbit Flight List @ 10:53:26

Thu 09 Jan AeroDomine LIRF Load Traffic: Departure WFE: 00:00 UNIT: 1234 proposals: Airlines: DELAY E/C/SATA MPR Fcst: Alt: NM Auto Refresh: GO

ENTRY #	ARCID	ATYP	ADEP	ADEN	D	RM	T	U	LOBT	WFE:	UNIT:	1234	proposals:	Airlines:	DELAY	E/C/SATA	MPR	SOBT	P/TOBT	P/TT	ARCID	ADEP	ADEN	D	RM	T	U	LOBT	WFE:	UNIT:	1234	proposals:	Airlines:	DELAY	E/C/SATA	MPR	SOBT	P/TOBT	P/TT	ARCID	ADEP	ADEN	D	RM	T	U	LOBT	WFE:	UNIT:	1234	proposals:	Airlines:	DELAY	E/C/SATA	MPR	SOBT	P/TOBT	P/TT
0512A	BAW539	BAW	AZDN	LIRF	EGLL	GTNXX	E	09-0505	05:17E	05:00	05:00	17	05:12A	07:31A	BAW538	EGLL	2321	10	23:31	BAW538	EGLL	2321	10	23:31																																		
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0523A	AFR138P	AFR	A320	LIRF	LFPG	FGKXY	E	09-0500	05:24C	05:07	05:10	14	05:23A	07:05A	AFR138P	LFPG	2129	7	21:36	AFR138P	LFPG	2129	7	21:36																																		
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0534A	WMT2381	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	LELL	9HNDQ	E	09-0510	05:31E	05:10	05:12	21	05:34A	06:46A	WMT2381	LELL	1716	9	17:25	WMT2381	LELL	1716	9	17:25																																		
0537A	WMT9XM	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	GCTS	9HNDI	E	09-0530	05:38E	05:22	05:24	11	05:37A	09:57A	WMT9XM	GCTS	2335	9	23:41	WMT9XM	GCTS	2335	9	23:41																																		
0539A	VLG23RQ	VLG	A320	LIRF	LEMG	ECMER	E	09-0515	05:39C	05:19	05:25	14	05:39A	08:05A	VLG23RQ	LEMG	1538	7	15:45	VLG23RQ	LEMG	1538	7	15:45																																		
0539A	RFR6EF	RFR	B738	LIRF	EDW	9HODJ	E	09-0525	05:39C	05:19	05:25	14	05:39A	08:05A	RFR6EF	EDW	0731	8	07:39	RFR6EF	EDW	0731	8	07:39																																		
0544A	MSA711	MSA	B738	LIRF	LMMI	EGVIN	E	09-0545	05:43E	05:30	05:30	12	05:44A	06:43A	MSA711	LMMI	0731	8	07:39	MSA711	LMMI	0731	8	07:39																																		
0551A	WMT1QP	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	ESKK	9HWAL	E	09-0535	05:47E	05:35	05:35	12	05:51A	07:58A	WMT1QP	ESKK	1543	9	15:52	WMT1QP	ESKK	1543	9	15:52																																		
0555A	WMT7SR	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	LKPR	9HWJQ	E	09-0540	05:52E	05:40	05:40	12	05:55A	07:14A	WMT7SR	LKPR	0235	7	02:32	WMT7SR	LKPR	0235	7	02:32																																		
0559A	AEZ100N	AEZ	B738	LIRF	LIEE	9HGAE	E	09-0550	05:58E	05:45	05:45	13	05:59A	06:43A	AEZ100N	LIEE	2109	8	21:17	AEZ100N	LIEE	2109	8	21:17																																		
0606A	THY2BV	THY	B739	LIRF	LTFM	TCJVA	E	09-0555	05:56E	05:42	05:42	14	06:06A	08:06A	THY2BV	LTFM	2049	15	21:04	THY2BV	LTFM	2049	15	21:04																																		
0608A	VLG6228	VLG	A320	LIRF	ESKK	ECMWE	E	09-0545	06:01C	05:45	05:45	16	06:08A	08:11A	VLG6228	ESKK	2249	8	22:57	VLG6228	ESKK	2249	8	22:57																																		
0611A	ITY2010	ITY	A320	LIRF	LIML	EHOL	E	09-0600	06:04E	05:54	05:54	12	06:11A	06:58A	ITY2010	LIML	1919	8	19:29	ITY2010	LIML	1919	8	19:29																																		
0613A	TAY9LA	TAY	B734	LIRF	LMMI	OEAE	E	09-0600	06:05E	06:00	06:00	15	06:13A	07:22A	TAY9LA	LMMI	0513	7	05:20	TAY9LA	LMMI	0513	7	05:20																																		
0615A	WMT4005	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	LFPO	9HNNK	E	09-0555	06:07	06:01	06:01	12	06:15A	07:59A	WMT4005	LFPO	2230	10	22:40	WMT4005	LFPO	2230	10	22:40																																		
0616A	VLG6255	VLG	A320	LIRF	LFPO	EDJUC	E	09-0540	06:10C	05:40	05:52	12	06:16A	07:59A	VLG6255	LFPO	1130	7	11:37	VLG6255	LFPO	1130	7	11:37																																		
0618A	RFR6ZD	RFR	B738	LIRF	LMMI	EDCWC	E	09-0610	06:15E	06:00	06:03	12	06:18A	07:29A	RFR6ZD	LMMI	0957	8	10:05	RFR6ZD	LMMI	0957	8	10:05																																		
0620A	WMT3JU	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	LRSV	9HWDR	E	09-0610	06:15E	06:03	06:04	11	06:20A	08:06A	WMT3JU	LRSV	2232	9	22:41	WMT3JU	LRSV	2232	9	22:41																																		
0625A	VLG6105	VLG	A320	LIRF	LEBL	ECNOC	E	09-0610	06:18E	06:10	06:10	14	06:25A	07:55A	VLG6105	LEBL	2204	9	22:13	VLG6105	LEBL	2204	9	22:13																																		
0629A	TAP319	TAP	A319	LIRF	LPPT	CSTTS	E	09-0500	06:40C	05:00	06:16	14	06:29A	09:20A	TAP319	LPPT	2236	10	22:46	TAP319	LPPT	2236	10	22:46																																		
0640A	DLH4RW	DLH	A321	LIRF	EDDF	DAIDJ	E	09-0605	06:40C	06:05	06:28	12	06:40A	08:12A	DLH4RW	EDDF	2153	9	22:02	DLH4RW	EDDF	2153	9	22:02																																		
0642A	WMT619	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	EHEH	9HWAK	E	09-0625	06:38E	06:25	06:25	13	06:42A	08:24A	WMT619	EHEH	1910	9	19:19	WMT619	EHEH	1910	9	19:19																																		
0645A	BAW551	BAW	A320	LIRF	EGLL	GTNTP	E	09-0635	06:49E	06:30	06:30	19	06:45A	08:58A	BAW551	EGLL	2046	11	20:57	BAW551	EGLL	2046	11	20:57																																		
0647A	WMT652	WMT	AZIN	LIRF	LPPT	9HWDH	E	09-0455	06:24C	04:51	06:40	14	06:47A	09:39A	WMT652	LPPT	2201	11	22:12	WMT652	LPPT	2201	11	22:12																																		
0651A	IBE61P	IBE	A321	LIRF	LEMD	ECHUH	E	09-0630	06:44E	06:30	06:33	14	06:51A	09:09A	IBE61P	LEMD	2258	7	23:05	IBE61P	LEMD	2258	7	23:05																																		
0653A	AEZ300Z	AEZ	B738	LIRF	LIEE	9HMAH	E	09-0650	06:51E	06:41	06:42	9	06:53A	07:37A	AEZ300Z	LIEE	0540	8	05:44	AEZ300Z	LIEE	0540	8	05:44																																		
0702A	RFR6TB	RFR	B738	LIRF	LEBO	EDLCC	E	09-0655	07:01E	06:47	06:47	14	07:02A	07:44A	RFR6TB	LEBO	0554	9	06:03	RFR6TB	LEBO	0554	9	06:03																																		

162 Flights

Details On Log A/C Rotation Quick Info Airframe Schedule Prediction History

Figure 5: A screenshot of one of the functionalities of the testing platform that has been developed to test model performance using live operational data. On the left-hand side of the visualisation, details about outbound flights are provided, including actual releases of TOBT and their predicted values. Instead, the right side presents information on inbound flights, including estimated arrival times (sourced from ETFS).

Figure 6: Results from the ongoing shadow mode live trials describing model performance at the network level measured during the week 13th–19th January 2025. Values above the bars indicate the percentage number of TOBT values, with respect to the total of the day, that either the model (first value) predicts or that the users (second value) provide (extracted either as TOBT itself or as the difference between the TTOT and the taxi-out).

Figure 7 presents the SHAP summary plot, highlighting the most influential input features. *Available Turnaround Time* emerges as the most impactful feature, with higher values (red) associated with longer predicted turnaround durations. This duration, as defined in this study, is the difference between the final TOBT value and the in-block time (Table I). Notably, the number of boarding passengers also ranks among the top features, indicating that the model has learned that turnaround duration tends to increase with passenger count. Additionally, the model appears to have benefited from the inclusion of delay-related inputs, as two delay features (*delay1* and *delay2*) rank high, suggesting improved predictive performance compared to the basic model.

Figure 7: Shapley summary plot showing feature importance and impact on model predictions. Color indicates feature value, and points represent Shapley values for individual instances.

VI. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The A-CDM process places the TOBT updater at its core, highlighting its crucial role. To reach substantial levels of local and network predictability, it is essential that a culture of early and accurate TOBT updates is ingrained among stakeholders operating at CDM airports [29]. While there is a well-recognized common effort towards sharing more accurate information, the TOBT updater might hesitate to provide early updates. This reluctance stems from the possibility of the flight being subjected to ATFM delay or incurring additional TSAT delay by shifting into a period of higher departure demand [29]. The current practice of manually inputting TOBT is prone to errors due to human factors, typos, and inefficient information flow, which often result in last-minute TOBT changes. It is well known that such last-minute adjustments could alter the TSAT value and trigger late Calculated takeoff Time (CTOT), leaving little room for improvement. Furthermore, the growing traffic forces most airports to operate near their infrastructural limits. Therefore, there is a need of accurate predictions of turnaround time and TOBT values which could help all the stakeholder operating at airports better allocate and manage ground resources improving overall efficiency in flight operations.

In Section IV a ML model predicting turnaround duration and TOBT for all CDM airports and airlines operating from them was presented. Results showed that 66% of predictions released at the beginning or during the turnaround do not require any update by an operational user with a MAE of 4.3 minutes. Overall, results in Section IV-B show that model

predictions tend to be more accurate than TOBT values shared via DPI messages up to 40/50 minutes before takeoff which is typically the critical timeframe for effectively optimizing and allocating airport resources.

Good model performance observed during a disrupted day (Section IV-C) was in line with expectations. This is because the model's update mechanism relies primarily on the estimated arrival times provided by ETFMS and the ability to accurately associate inbound and outbound flight legs. The latter depends on the stability and consistency of flight plans filed by airlines. When these two conditions are met, even in disrupted scenarios, the model can maintain reliable performance by effectively updating its predictions based on real-time operational inputs.

In the second validation exercise, model predictions showed a closer alignment with the values provided by users. This improvement is likely due to the broader and more representative dataset used during this phase. Unlike the first validation, which focused solely on extracting TOBT values, the second exercise also incorporated a proxy for TOBT, calculated as the difference between TTOT and taxi-out time. For flights experiencing minimal or no delays, this proxy offers a reasonable estimate of the actual TOBT, resulting in a noticeable improvement in the quality of user-provided metrics, particularly in the time window from four to two hours before takeoff. Although this convergence was anticipated, it is nonetheless encouraging to observe that the model maintained stable and comparable performance in these updated testing conditions.

The feedback from the stakeholders, collected via a survey after the first validation exercise, was positive, highlighting that the model predictions offer significant advantages for operational processes, enabling more streamlined ground handling operations. Furthermore, ongoing live trials are confirming the model metrics that have been measured during the development and the first validation exercise. This is proving the model's ability to generalize to new time periods beyond the training data. In addition to its immediate application, the model might serve as a key component for further models requiring accurate turnaround time information as an input. While further analyses during ongoing trials are necessary, results start suggesting that the model might be used in an operational setting where the initial TOBT values are generated by the model, allowing ground handlers or airlines to update them if needed. This approach has already been implemented at Prague Airport based on the results of a previous project [7].

The predictive capabilities of the developed model can serve as a complementary tool to existing or planned camera-based monitoring systems adopted by several airports for turnaround management. While camera-based systems provide real-time, image-driven detection of specific ground events, they may be limited by factors such as visibility conditions, occlusions, or infrastructure constraints. In contrast, the model leverages historical and operational data to produce early and continuous estimates of key turnaround milestones.

By integrating both approaches, airports can benefit from enhanced situational awareness: camera systems offer detailed, event-level observations, while data-driven models provide predictive insights that support proactive decision-making and improved resource allocation. This hybrid setup strengthens the overall robustness and resilience of turnaround monitoring systems.

The case presented in Section V investigates how passenger and delay data, provided by Austrian Airlines and by the Eurocontrol CODA team, affect the accuracy of TOBT predictions. It was shown that the model trained with the inclusion of these data enhances the performance of a basic model (trained without passenger and delay data) by 10% in terms of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and by 7% regarding the percentage of predictions with errors within a +/- 5 minute window. The basic model (Table III) featured already good performance (especially when compared to overall results in Figure 1). It might be, instead, expected that the performance improvement observed from incorporating passenger and delay information will be higher when starting from a less accurate basic model. This hypothesis can be tested in the future, as additional data from other airlines becomes available. The models were developed under the assumption that the inputs are available at the AIBT of the inbound flight and as soon as ground delays materialise. However, this might not be fully realistic. Therefore, additional considerations may be necessary for deploying such a model in an operational environment.

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